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Abstract: This deliverable is a report on all train-the-trainer bootcamps organised by T6.4 within the duration of the project. The deliverable sets out to evaluate the SSHOC train-the-trainer Bootcamps that took place between June 2020 and May 2021 as originally planned in the SSHOC *Building Expertise Strategy*.

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Executive Summary

Training is an important aspect of knowledge acquisition and transfer in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud project (SSHOC). For successful implementation and promotion of the SSH Open Cloud, it is crucial to empower users, and to facilitate mutual learning and networking among data producers, users, and experts. Therefore, the SSHOC Training Community has been established. It aims to facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration between experts who provide training to scholars in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) on tools and services offered by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

As part of various training formats during the SSHOC project lifecycle, T6.4 has conducted a series of bootcamps. These four events were directed at different stakeholder groups, primarily research libraries and archives, universities, and research-performing institutions. The bootcamps covered a broad range of topics and tools relevant for Open Science and Research Data Management and for conducting training in those fields.

This deliverable reports the outcomes of the bootcamps that, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, took place online. Chapter two brings individual bootcamp reports that provide deeper insights into structure, topics, and stakeholder representation. Since the final bootcamp, co-located with the IASSIST conference, was organised in May 2021 due to the original postponement of the IASSIST conference, the final deliverable describing the bootcamps (D6.12) as well as the deliverable of the final version of the toolkit (D6.11) and its related milestone (MS41) were delayed.

In the following chapters, a reflection of all the bootcamps is provided together with a compilation of lessons learned and best practices for setting up online events.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CESSDA	Consortium European Social Sciences Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
KNAW-DANS	Dutch National Centre of Expertise and Repository for Research Data
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EIFL	Electronic Information for Libraries
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR data	Data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FOSTER	Facilitate Open Science Training for European Research
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GESIS	GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
IASSIST	International Association for Social Science Information Service and Technology
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
RDM	Research Data Management
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	6
2. Bootcamp Reports	9
2.1 Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit	9
2.2 SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians at LIBER Annual Conference 2020	10
2.3 SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at IASSIST 2021	13
2.4 SSHOC Train-the-Trainer RDM Bootcamp Jointly Organised by SSHOC and DARIAH	16
3. Summary and Outcomes	20
3.1 Moving Online: Potentials and Challenges	20
3.2 Lessons Learned	22
3.3 Best Practices	23
3.4 Stakeholder Representation and Satisfaction	26
4. Conclusion	29
References	30
List of Tables	31
List of Figures	31
Appendix – Further Information on Bootcamp Evaluations	32

1. Introduction

Empowering users and building expertise in Open Science and Research Data Management-related topics in the Social Sciences and Humanities plays a central role in the SSHOC project WP (Work Package) 6. The train-the-trainer bootcamps, organised jointly with a number of organisations involved in the SSHOC project, provided key engagement and knowledge sharing opportunities for the organising and participating representatives of research infrastructures and institutes in the SSH. The train-the-trainer bootcamps assisted in building the SSHOC Training Community and were a great opportunity for the promotion of SSHOC in the EU and beyond.

A bootcamp differs from a workshop in its format and goals as it aims not only to present new information, but also to develop participants' skills through an interactive and practice-oriented approach. The SSHOC Training Community, created and facilitated by T6.4 throughout the project, thrives on the involvement of its members and focuses on building their skills and expertise in a number of ways. In that respect, the train-the-trainer bootcamps served as a valuable tool for expanding and strengthening the SSHOC Training Community by targeting SSH trainers from the community and beyond. The overall goal of the train-the-trainer bootcamps was knowledge exchange between SSH trainers and building skills on a wide variety of topics, such as:

- FAIR data principles for RDM;
- Research Ethics: Data protection and Ethical issues in working with social media data;
- Dealing with third-party data coming from Cultural Heritage institutions (galleries, museums, libraries, archives);
- Tools for checking numeric data: data health check tool which enables researchers to assess the quality of their data and supports repositories and archives in setting up a health profile for data accepted;
- Introducing Open Science platforms, e.g. The FOSTER e-learning platform and other reusable training materials;
- Guidelines on how to organise own trainings, both from the organisational and didactics perspectives;
- Presentation of SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit: a discovery tool for trainers in the SSH where they can find training materials to reuse and improve their own training;
- CLARIN resources, tools and services in order to offer support to researchers, students, lecturers and citizen scientists in answering their research questions;
- Bringing events online: practical advice for training coordinators.

The knowledge and skills transfer during the bootcamps was two-sided, as it happened from SSHOC partners to the community, as well as the other way around. Bootcamp participants gave the SSHOC organisers the opportunity to receive feedback regarding the presented tools. Group discussions often served as ideas for the work of WP6. This dialogue between the SSHOC partners and the Training

Community is highly valuable: continuous improvement of the tools in the EOSC landscape is crucial to the overall success of Open Science practices in the European Union.

Originally, three on-site train-the-trainer bootcamps were planned to help trainers develop and improve their own training activities. They were scheduled for a duration of at least 1.5 days per bootcamp and were to be co-organised with local partners or co-hosted at conferences. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the original plans had to be amended and bootcamps had to be held online. The original plan was to co-locate bootcamps with two major conferences: IASSIST Conference in May 2020 and LIBER Annual Conference in June 2020. The 2020 IASSIST conference was postponed to 2021, whereas LIBER moved its annual conference online, allowing T6.4 to co-locate an online bootcamp. The Mini Bootcamp and the SSHOC DARIAH Train-the-Trainer RDM Bootcamp were executed as stand-alone events.

While moving bootcamps online due to the COVID-19 pandemic was challenging, particularly given the engaging format bootcamps would otherwise provide, the mitigation plan was created to accommodate flexible and creative training approaches and turn in-person bootcamps into online ones. As part of the plan, T6.4 decided to use the opportunity and organise three online train-the-trainer bootcamps. A Mini Bootcamp about the SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit served as a first trial of an online bootcamp and was exclusively offered to the SSH Training Community. This change allowed for the inclusion of the Training Community and provided more opportunities for interaction and networking between its members, particularly in times of the pandemic when such opportunities are limited. Transferring all the bootcamps into the digital space required customising familiar formats: online teaching (didactic sessions, presentations on how to effectively deliver information online), interactive elements (group work, Q&A, case studies) and individual learning (homework assignments) were carried out to the participants' satisfaction.

The final bootcamp was organised in May 2021 at IASSIST online conference, originally postponed from 2020. The co-location brought opportunities to attract specific audiences that would otherwise be difficult to reach, thus justifying the delay.

Despite the challenging circumstances, the bootcamps' participants, including the members of the SSHOC Training Community, were engaged rather well online. The bootcamps were able to reach a diverse audience both in terms of profession and location. Efforts to make sure the interaction remains interesting and engaging despite the pandemic were intensified and plans for monthly rather than originally planned bi-monthly meetings were created. The SSHOC training website¹ provides an overview of activities.

¹ SSHOC Training Website: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/training> [accessed Oct 2021].

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW OF THE BOOTCAMPS INCLUDING REFERENCES TO TRAINING RESOURCES AND BLOG POSTS

Bootcamp	Date	Number of Participants	Links to Corresponding Documents and Blog Posts
Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit	2 June 2020	17	No public training resources available. ² Blog post: https://sshopencloud.eu/news/first-sshoc-training-community-mini-bootcamp
SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians at the LIBER Annual Conference 2020	23 June 2020	51	Training resources: https://zenodo.org/record/3970799#.YXqgo5rP2Mp Blog post: https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/boost-research-librarians-sshoc-train-trainer-bootcamp
SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at IASSIST 2021	12 May 2021	52	Training resources: https://zenodo.org/record/4813115#.YXqhG5rP2Mo Blog post: https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/highlights-sshoc-open-science-and-research-data-management-train-trainer-bootcamp
SSHOC Train-the-Trainer RDM Bootcamp jointly organised by SSHOC and DARIAH	8 and 11 February 2021	90	Training resources: https://zenodo.org/communities/sshocdariahtrainerrdmbootcamp/?page=1&size=20 Blog post: https://sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-dariah-train-trainer-research-data-management-bootcamp-0

² These training resources are not publicly available because the bootcamp was organised as an exclusive event for members of the SSHOC Training Community who can still access the material.

2. Bootcamp Reports

2.1 Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit

BACKGROUND

This report concerns one of the train-the-trainer events run by the SSHOC project. The event was titled *Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit* and was held on the 2nd of June 2020. Different reasons led to organising this mini bootcamp. First, the COVID-19 crisis started to have its impact so that the planned bootcamp at the IASSIST conference in June 2020 was postponed to 2021. Second, the Training Discovery Toolkit was close to its first launch and third, the Training Community for trainers that SSHOC WP6.4 initiated had its first kick-off call. Since it was not possible to invite the community to the IASSIST conference to offer a full demo of the Training Discovery Toolkit, it was decided to organise an online mini bootcamp specifically for the Training Community on the Training Discovery Toolkit.

WORKSHOP OVERVIEW & FORMAT

The aim of this mini bootcamp was to provide train-the-trainer support to the members of the Training Community by offering the Training Discovery Toolkit and to give them the opportunity to provide feedback on the Training Discovery Toolkit. The mini bootcamp was announced in the Training Community calls, but not on the SSHOC website publicly. The organisers handled this online event as an 'exclusive' event, only to be attended by members of the Training Community. The mini bootcamp was organised specifically by KNAW-DANS and LIBER and was hosted by LIBER.

There were no external speakers involved. Ellen Leenarts provided a short introduction to the project and the programme. Ricarda Braukmann provided a presentation on the Training Discovery Toolkit with use cases and introduced the feedback using a google form and the breakout groups. Tatsiana Yankelevich wrapped up the bootcamp. After two days of feedback response time, a short feedback report was created by Ellen Leenarts and shared with all the participants.

The participants of the mini bootcamp were all members of the SSHOC Training Community. At the time of the bootcamp it had 60 members. In total 25 members registered for the mini bootcamp and 17 attended, including the organisers. The bootcamp was a train-the-trainer activity focused on trainers in research performing organisations and research infrastructures.

PRESENTATIONS & DISCUSSIONS: KEY POINTS

After a short introduction the main presentation was provided by Ricarda Braukmann explaining the goal of the new Training Discovery Toolkit and how to use it. After this presentation the participants were divided into three groups and discussed detailing the structure, the look and feel and the overall idea of the Training Discovery Toolkit.

OUTCOMES & FEEDBACK

All feedback on the SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit has been taken into consideration by T6.4 to improve the tool. The organisers of the event were generally happy with the results and with the format being an all-online event. Participants contributed well to the breakout sessions and provided valuable feedback and points for discussion. Breakouts worked well for knowledge exchange, introducing the tool and receiving feedback. One of the attendants wrote a blog on the Mini Bootcamp³ with positive feedback. The blog was published on the SSHOC website and announced via Twitter.

2.2 SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians at the LIBER Annual Conference 2020

BACKGROUND

The *SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians* at the LIBER Annual Conference 2020 was held on Tuesday 23rd of June 2020. This bootcamp focused on Librarians as the target audience.

WORKSHOP OVERVIEW & FORMAT

The workshop was part of the LIBER Online 2020 conference held during the week of 22nd June 2020.⁴ The bootcamp was one of the workshops offered as part of the conference programme. The bootcamp consisted of three different parts.

Firstly, the SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit was introduced. Then a hands-on session on CLARIN materials was organised where participants could work on use cases using the CLARIN repository resources. Lastly, the workshop concluded with a session on organizing events online, exchanging best practices and methodologies.

The event was organised by SSHOC partners LIBER, CLARIN and KNAW-DANS. In particular Tatsiana Yankelevich, Vasso Kalaitzi (LIBER), Darja Fišer, Jakob Lenardič, Elisa Gorgaini (CLARIN), Ellen Leenarts & Ricarda Braukmann (KNAW-DANS) were involved in the organization.

In total 58 people had registered which was the maximum of participants allowed to register. In the end, 51 participants were present. Out of these, 31 participants identified themselves as belonging to the

³ See blog post: First SSHOC Training Community Mini Bootcamp: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/first-sshoc-training-community-mini-bootcamp> [accessed Oct 2021].

⁴ LIBER Online 2020: <https://libereurope.eu/events/liber-2020-annual-conference> [accessed Oct 2021].

research libraries and archives stakeholder group, 15 as universities and research-performing institutions, 2 as research and e-infrastructures, 1 as civil society and citizen scientist and 1 as researcher. Participants came from 17 different countries, including outside of the EU, like Belarus and India. Participants' current position was assessed using Mentimeter confirming that indeed most participants were Librarians.

PRESENTATIONS & DISCUSSIONS: KEY POINTS

The Bootcamp consisted of the following three parts:

- The SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit
- Hands-on session on CLARIN Tools
- Bringing events online

Prior to the first presentation, a brief introduction was given covering the house rules and a general overview of the work of SSHOC and CLARIN. In addition, participants were asked about their current profession through a Mentimeter question. It was intended to also collect information on the participants' country but due to technical problems this question could not be displayed, and no data was collected.

The SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit - Ricarda Braukmann (KNAW-DANS)

This presentation provided a brief overview of the SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit⁵, a discovery tool for trainers in the SSH where they can find training materials to reuse and improve their own training. The toolkit was showcased by means of a use case selected for this event, namely "I am looking for materials to aid researchers interested in language data." The presentation showed how someone looking for language data could use the toolkit to find resources. The CLARIN Resource Families were shown as an example. After the presentation, there was time for questions from the audience. Many participants got involved and asked, for instance, about the plans for adding new materials, about current plans around sustainability and about including thesauri in an updated version of the toolkit.

Hands-on session about CLARIN tools - Darja Fišer (CLARIN ERIC)

The second part of the bootcamp started with a screencast about the CLARIN tools and integrated services, which helped the participants familiarise themselves with various CLARIN services (used to conduct different kinds of linguistic analyses). Then a practical session followed to directly engage with the resources, tools and services offered by the CLARIN infrastructure. The aim of this session was for participants to familiarise themselves with the CLARIN resources, tools, and services in order to offer support to researchers, students, lecturers and citizen scientists in answering their research questions.

⁵ SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit: www.training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu [accessed Oct 2021].

Participants could choose between one of two scenarios which were each described in handout documents provided through the online system. The participants followed a step-by-step guide answering one of two different research questions via searching the CLARIN repository⁶ and exploring CLARIN resource families.⁷ The handouts were made available after the session to encourage the participants to make use of the instructions when needed in their daily work. At the end of this hands-on session, there was room for questions and participants were able to ask questions to CLARIN staff using the chat function.

Bringing events online - Tatsiana Yankelevich (LIBER)

The last part of the bootcamp focused on bringing events online. Tatsiana Yankelevich started with a presentation⁸ giving practical advice to the audience, which was followed by a discussion and exchange of experiences. The presentation featured the importance of strategic session design and effective use of different formats online. It further focused on housekeeping rules and of good ice-breaker moments, for instance by using online polling tools. The audience engaged in a discussion about the value of pre-recorded content. This was seen as valuable to provide additional information to participants, but has the disadvantage of being less interactive than a live presentation. Different ways to achieve interactivity in online sessions was another discussion point. Dealing with the uncertainties of the pandemic in the planning of future events and choosing between hosting online, offline or hybrid events was also brought up by an audience member. A document summarizing the advice given in the presentation and providing more in-depth information on organizing events online was provided to participants through the online system and made available on Zenodo.

OUTCOMES AND FEEDBACK

The maximum number of registrations was reached relatively quickly, and the registration had to be closed showing that the interest in the bootcamp existed within the community. Fifty-one people attended the event and most of them were from the target audience (librarians).

The event was used to increase the awareness of the SSHOC and CLARIN tools and has succeeded in this aim. Participants were interested in the content that was presented and actively engaged in the discussions. It was valuable to discuss questions about the Training Discovery Toolkit and, about the

⁶ CLARIN Repository: <https://vlo.clarin.eu/?jsessionid=922FA812E67C4F96D6C2DA6966AC2283?0> [accessed Oct 2021].

⁷ CLARIN Resource Families initiative: <https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families> [accessed Oct 2021].

⁸ The bootcamp materials are available on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/3921857#.YVqvAzHP2Mo> [accessed Oct 2021].

sustainability and integration with other resources being developed in the EOSC landscape. These will be taken up as points of attention for the future.

An evaluation was sent to participants after the event⁹. All respondents said that the event either met or exceeded their expectations. In addition, all respondents said that the event was either well (56%) or excellently organised (44%). A total 55% of respondents explicitly confirmed that the event had a positive impact on their work. Suggestions for improvements included longer sessions, including more hand-on parts and more time for interactions and personal contact with other attendees. The experiences from this bootcamp were used in the development of the other ones. The slides of the event as well as the handout on organizing online events and CLARIN exercise handouts are available on Zenodo.¹⁰

2.3 SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at IASSIST 2021

BACKGROUND

The event was titled *SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp* and was held on the 10th and 12th of May 2021 as a pre-conference workshop part of the IASSIST 2021 Conference.

WORKSHOP OVERVIEW & FORMAT

The bootcamp aimed to aid trainers in finding resources and tools they can re-use in their training activities. It was held virtually, over Zoom, with two-hour sessions. The bootcamp was organised by SSHOC partners KNAW-DANS, LIBER and UKDS. Trainers from the FAIRsFAIR project and FOSTER project were invited as external trainers. On day one, 54 participants attended and on day two, 34 participants attended.

⁹ The survey was filled in by nine participants.

¹⁰ Yankelevich, T., Fiser, D., Lenardic, J., Gorgaini, E., & Braukmann, R. (2020). LIBER 2020 - Workshop: SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3970799> [accessed Oct 2021].

PRESENTATIONS & DISCUSSIONS: KEY POINTS

Day one:

Welcome and Introduction - Tatsiana Yankelevich (LIBER)

Tatsiana Yankelevich, Training Coordinator at LIBER, kicked off the bootcamp with an interactive introductory session. The SSHOC project was introduced to the audience and the outline of the bootcamp was presented.

Tools for checking numeric data - Cristina Magder, Anca Vlad & Hina Zahid (UKDS)

The speakers presented two tools for assessing numeric data. The presentation looked at “QAMyData”, a data health check tool which enables researchers to assess the quality of their data and supports repositories and archives in setting up a health profile for data accepted. The presentation also included a quick glance at statistical disclosure control freeware with a focus on the “sdcMicro Graphical User Interface”, the tool of choice at UKDS.

The FAIR Aware Tool - Linas Cepinskas (KNAW-DANS/FAIRsFAIR) & Joy Davidson (DCC/FAIRsFAIR)

The speakers gave an overview of the FAIR-Aware tool. This is a non-disciplinary focused online tool developed by the FAIRsFAIR project. The tool can be adapted by different communities for their own use. It helps researchers and data managers assess how much they know about the requirements for making datasets findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) before sharing them.

The DANS Data Game - Ricarda Braukmann (KNAW-DANS)

Ricarda Braukmann showcased the “KNAW-DANS Data Game” which gives a great interactive overview of the common and most used research data concepts. The game was produced for the 15th anniversary of KNAW-DANS. The idea of the game is to play smart and collect as many sets of four cards on RDM and FAIR and Open data as possible by interacting with other players.

Didactics and FOSTER train-the-trainer materials - Iryna Kuchma (EIFL)

Iryna Kuchma presented a didactics session including looking at the available FOSTER materials. The FOSTER e-learning platform is a portal that gathers the best open science resources.

Introduction to the homework assignment - Ellen Leenarts (KNAW-DANS)

Ellen Leenarts from KNAW-DANS introduced the bootcamp homework which participants have had to prepare in between the days. The main aim of the homework was to give participants time to investigate the tools and practices presented and for them to create a structure for a new training session that integrates one of the presented tools.

Day two:

Breakout session one: Tools for checking numeric data

The breakout room was well attended with a mixture of participants from both Europe and the USA. The participants highlighted how challenging teaching on curating and quality assessing data can be. While they have recognised that introducing new tools could potentially be overwhelming, most agreed their target audiences, which in general were students and early career researchers, would embrace and use the tools. Several attendants have completed the homework and were looking at introducing both the tools for checking data and the FAIR Aware tool as part of their training sessions. Discussing the worst-case scenarios has been very lively and not only participants, but the presenters have benefited from hearing of different solutions others have in place to ensure training is delivered as expected.

Breakout session two: The FAIR Aware Tool

The breakout session welcomed a diverse group of data professionals, funders, and policy makers from across the world. Participants actively shared their experiences in communicating the FAIR data principles and training researchers on how to translate these principles in practice. They recognised that researchers often underestimate the consequences of not sharing research data. As a solution, they proposed several suggestions, such as using real-life examples and emphasising practical benefits of FAIR data, building a safe and engaging environment for FAIR data practices by connecting senior researchers with early career researchers.

Participants found the FAIR-Aware tool practical and useful for their training activities. As part of the homework assignment, they offered a number of useful suggestions for integrating the tool in training activities. These suggestions will be used to create (new) training resources around the tool.

Session three: The DANS Data Game

The breakout room was attended by a small but enthusiastic group of scholars based in the US, UK and Europe. Participants and hosts exchanged about potential uses of the DANS Data Game and demonstrated a quiz that has been implemented in Mentimeter and is based on the cards from the game. Participants shared ideas on how the game could be further developed and discussed its usefulness for teaching students the basics of RDM. One of the participants mentioned a call for creating online games which could be used to further develop the online version of the DANS Data Game.

Reflection on the breakout sessions

The plenary session allowed the presenters to summarise the breakout rooms and also reflect on the tools they have presented. While the attendees learnt about the new tools, the presenters were able to implement changes and think of future planning based on the feedback received. For example, for the QAMyData tool it was highlighted that the webpage might benefit from a disclaimer that the tool is locally run, showing that the stored data is safe and not transferred anywhere.

The SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit - Ricarda Braukmann (KNAW-DANS)

Ricarda Braukmann has presented the SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit and demonstrated how to find training materials for re-use which has been received very well by the audience.

OUTCOMES AND FEEDBACK

Feedback has been gathered centrally via an IASSIST standard form. Informal feedback was gathered via Mentimeter polls. The participants described the event as collaborative and interesting; they reported to have enjoyed the presentations, the breakout rooms and the homework. Results from both the IASSIST feedback form and the Mentimeter polls are available in the appendix.

Introducing tools, common techniques and exercises for training delivery was well received by the attendees. Several reported that they will use the tools in their own training. Presenting the SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit has facilitated further promotion of SSHOC and has reached people from very diverse institutions. Given that this was the very first remote IASSIST conference, the organisation of the event went well. However, as the registration was part of IASSIST conference online registration form, information that could have helped assess the bootcamp has not been gathered (e.g., the participants' research discipline).

2.4 SSHOC Train-the-Trainer RDM Bootcamp Jointly Organised by SSHOC and DARIAH

BACKGROUND

The event was titled *Train-the-trainer RDM Bootcamp* and co-organised by SSHOC and DARIAH-EU. It was held on the 8th and 11th of February 2021 as a two-day virtual bootcamp. The event has a dedicated Zenodo community¹¹ page where the slides of the main sessions are stored.

From the SSHOC project task 6.4, Tatsiana Yankelevich (LIBER), Ricarda Braukmann (KNAW-DANS), Ellen Leenarts (KNAW-DANS) and Veronika Keck (GESIS) were involved in the organisation. From DARIAH-EU, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra and Victoria Garnett were involved.

¹¹ Zenodo community for the SSHOC Train-the-Trainer RDM Bootcamp jointly organised by SSHOC and DARIAH : <https://zenodo.org/communities/sshocdariahtrainerrdmbootcamp?page=1&size=20> [accessed Oct 2021].

For the thematic sessions, the following trainers were invited: Kristen Schuster (King's College London, UK), Katrin Weller and Oliver Watteler (GESIS, Germany), Angus Whyte, Joy Davidson and Ryan O'Connor (Digital Curation Centre, UK), Annalisa Montesanti (Health Research Board, Ireland) and Kerstin Helbig (Humboldt Universität zu Berlin).

WORKSHOP OVERVIEW AND FORMAT

This SSHOC bootcamp was designed as a two times two-hour online event. After the first day, participants were given homework assignments for their chosen topic.

The bootcamp was based on three topics of which the participants could choose one to focus on, and an additional didactical component to cater to the training needs of the participants. The following lectures took place during the first day of the bootcamp:

1. Planning to meet the costs of managing research data to be FAIR.
Invited trainers: Angus Whyte, Joy Davidson, Ryan O'Connor (Digital Curation Centre, UK), Annalisa Montesanti (Health Research Board, Ireland).
2. GDPR and ethical issues in working with social media data.
Invited trainers: Katrin Weller, Oliver Watteler (GESIS, Germany).
3. Dealing with third-party data coming from Cultural Heritage institutions (galleries, museums, libraries, archives).
Invited trainer: Kristen Schuster (King's College London, UK).

The first day, the bootcamp started with a short introduction of the SSHOC project and DARIAH, followed by a plenary session. The plenary was followed by three simultaneous topic-specific breakout room sessions to provide additional guidance and introduce the homework assignments. Once all participants returned to the main room, Kerstin Helbig from Humboldt University Berlin, Germany, introduced different homework assignments to the entire audience. This was a preparation for the *training concept development* presentation that took place during the second day of the bootcamp.

The second day of the bootcamp commenced with the same three topic-specific breakout groups. The breakouts lasted for an hour and provided participants and trainers a chance to discuss homework assignments and any remaining questions. The bootcamp finished with a 45-minute lecture on didactics (training concept development) and a wrap-up.

PARTICIPANTS

There were 90 participants that attended the bootcamp. Out of these 90 participants, one represented the civil society/citizen scientist category, four identified as research and e-infrastructures and EOSC thematic clusters, 30 came from research library and/or archive, seven were researchers and 48 identified as university and/or research performing organisation.

DETAILED DESCRIPTIONS OF THE SESSIONS

Planning to meet the costs of managing research data to be FAIR

This session offered training resources to adapt to individual institutional context, helping researchers to do the following:

- Understand why they should budget for the costs of making and keeping data FAIR, and include these costs in grant applications;
- Appreciate the benefits that services may provide to justify their costs;
- Know about the different kinds of data management costs, including costs that funding bodies may allow to be charged to projects;
- Apply a costing guide to help budget for the costs that may arise in preparing data to be FAIR;
- Share experiences and expectations about costs related to the preparation of FAIR data.

GDPR and ethical issues in working with social media data

Data that can be collected from social media and other web platforms are currently used as a new type of research data across academic disciplines, for example, to study online communication or to learn about users' behaviour. While the corresponding research area is growing, there are a lot of questions, e.g., about research methods or potential standards, to be answered. Discussions also increasingly focus on concerns about research ethics and data protection. A lot of work that is being done in this area is 'work in progress', and currently only a few standards or best practices on research designs or on documenting and sharing this type of research data exist.

In the session about GDPR and ethics in social media research, the participants were introduced to some key challenges related to questions of research ethics with a focus on data protection. Trainers drew attention to the critical issues of working with social media data as research material and recommended useful resources as references for further reading.

The presentation focused on the sensitive data, e.g., political orientation, protest movements, or online dating, as used in different research areas, e.g., communication science, computer science, linguistics, educational science, physics, medical science, sociology.

Five challenges for data protection and ethics in social media research were detected:

1. Usage of personal data/usage of sensitive data.
2. Missing consent from the social media users because they are not aware of the usage of their data for research.
3. There is no clear concept for public data and its usage.
4. Algorithms and computational research methods add novel challenges, e.g., usage of the same usernames, IDs, passwords.
5. Growing awareness in the research community

In the second presentation titled *Research ethics, data protection and the specific contexts for studying social media*, GESIS experts provided information about the research on ethics in the social sciences. They talked about data protection as part of a person's right to privacy. The authors introduced the legal framework in the European Union: Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (Art. 8) and the GDPR. They also touched upon topics of national and sub-national data protection acts and specialised laws.

Take-home messages from the experts on the GDPR and ethics:

- Questions about data protection and research ethics need to be included from the very beginning of a research study.
- Reserve capacities for this during research data management.
- Revisit decisions at later stages of the research process, especially if strategies have changed.

During the second day of the bootcamp, each group briefly presented their case studies by following the structure below:

- Short summary of the selected case study: research objective, data used.
- Challenges for data protection and research ethics.
- Suggestions for improvements and lessons learned.

At the end each group presented their opinions and open questions for discussion. The GDPR and ethics experts answered as many questions as they could within the given timeframe.

Dealing with third-party data coming from Cultural Heritage institutions (galleries, museums, libraries, archives)

The session started with a short summary of an ongoing research project exploring strategies practitioners and researchers use to communicate and collaborate and, ideally, share data based on mutually understood data management strategies. A key goal for this part of the session was to present, review and discuss strategies for enhancing communication about data management across disciplines within the DH and cultural heritage communities.

Training concept development

In the last session of the bootcamp, participants were guided through the seven steps of concept development by Kerstin Helbig from the Humboldt Universität. Participants had received the homework assignment to create a mind map of their own training, and these were used to showcase how a training can be further developed once the scope of the training has been mapped out. The participants were invited to ask questions and apply the presented content development steps to their own training activities.

RESULTS FROM THE EVALUATION

Fifteen participants filled in the evaluation form. All but one respondent indicated that they had participated in both days of the event, the remaining respondents indicated to have participated in the second day only. Overall, the event was positively evaluated. Four participants reviewed the event as excellent, five said it was very good or good and just one participant answered fair when rating the overall event. The organisation was evaluated as excellently or well organised by all but one respondent. Although 40% of the respondents indicated that the event did not meet their expectations, others reported that it exceeded or matched their expectations.

Responding to the question of what could have been better, the participants indicated that there was a lot of information presented but not enough time to digest. The participants expected more hands-on content and wished for longer break-out sessions.

About half of the participants stated that they had performed the assignments after the first day. The fact that not all participants will work on the assignments is an important take-away message for any future events. It should be noted, though, that in the open-ended feedback questions, the format of the event was assessed positively (i.e., two days with shorter sessions and time in between). More than half of the respondents agreed that the event had a positive impact on their work. In particular, several respondents reported that they received new ideas on how to organise training as well as new resources to use in their role as trainers.

3. Summary and Outcomes

3.1 Moving Online: Potentials and Challenges

As described above, the organisers were faced with the challenge to remodel the training formats from face-to-face to online. This new format had both its advantages and its challenges.

POTENTIALS

The biggest advantage of online events is reaching more international participants. For instance, the bootcamp evaluations indicate that even people from as far as India and the United States participated. If the bootcamps took place in a face-to-face format, participants from most of such geographically dispersed countries would have probably not been represented. Thus, the online train-the-trainer bootcamps fostered increased international networking among a broad range of nationalities, and SSHOC tools, events, and its community gained more attention.

Access to advanced technology and conference tools was a big advantage. Although they cannot fully replace face-to-face interactions, the meeting software enabled using a variety of training techniques. The bootcamp organisers gave their best to ensure interaction between them and the participants. After

a presentation, it was common to give the audience time for questions. The bootcamp evaluations show that people actively participated in the Q&A sessions. Breakout rooms made it possible to work in groups on different topics at the same time and facilitated networking between the participants. For instance, separate sessions proved to be beneficial to discuss the functionalities of specific research data management tools. These examples show that interactivity in a digital environment is possible, although it cannot replace face-to-face human interaction. Still, functions such as breakout rooms, the raise-your-hand button, the chat function, and survey tools (e.g., *Mentimeter*) allowed ongoing interaction during the bootcamps. Furthermore, offering several sessions with several days in between stimulated individual and group work, e.g., by offering homework assignments between the sessions.

The online format fostered inclusivity, allowing participants with restrictions and limitations of various natures (parental commitments, various disabilities and other health-related issues, institutional restrictions/commitments, or timing) to take part. This would not have been possible in face-to-face settings.

In terms of sustainability and the global challenge to fight climate change, such online events are an eco-friendly alternative: since nobody had to travel, emissions could be avoided and none of the participants increased his or her carbon footprint. The positive experience from the bootcamps will be considered for the planning of future events: evaluating whether it is necessary to meet in person is an important contribution to a responsible treatment of the planet.

Furthermore, the online events have saved time and budget. They were easier to handle in terms of administrative tasks. In this case, the SSHOC organisers did not have to take care of training facilities, catering, and accommodation. In terms of finances, travel funds remained unused as much as financial resources for the conference venue rental and the trainers' accommodation.

CHALLENGES

The bootcamp organisation and its implementation were largely affected by the sudden change from analogue to digital. Fundamental challenges were first, the use of new online conference tools and second, ensuring high quality of the bootcamps in an online environment.

Online events require well-structured planning and a plan B, in case of technical issues. The COVID-19 pandemic made planning processes complicated due to its unforeseeable nature. Therefore, all four bootcamps were conducted as online events. However, real human contact is irreplaceable in a training context. That impression corresponds with common participants' feedback that personal interaction was missing.

The bootcamp organisers managed to familiarise themselves with various virtual meeting and polling software, like GoToTraining, Zoom, GotoMeeting or Mentimeter, at a quick pace which allowed them to create a varied program with interactive elements. Technical issues occurred despite diligent preparation. For instance, in one of the bootcamps the data collection via Mentimeter did not work. In another case using the GoTo Training software, the participants' allocation to breakout rooms was

problematic. Even if the technical equipment on the part of the organisers works perfectly, there is still the risk that the participants experience issues with access to the meeting or internet connection problems.

A big challenge on an interpersonal level are limited networking opportunities and exchange aside from the bootcamps themselves. It was a different dynamic not being able to socialise during breaks over a cup of coffee. Such spontaneous encounters are important since they influence the participants' overall experience and indirect outcomes of the event such as new collaborations and training activities that naturally arise during face-to-face events.

3.2 Lessons Learned

The online formats of the bootcamps were an overall success. There is potential for growth, nevertheless. Based on the organisers' experiences and the participants' feedback, valuable lessons and best practices for future online events were derived. Areas for improvement largely concern interaction, structure and length of the sessions, event reporting and clarity of homework assignments.

INTERACTION

The evaluations indicate that participants highly value interaction among each other. A lack of interaction with other attendees reduces the overall satisfaction with the bootcamps. Participants wish for both more networking opportunities and for more frequent and longer group work in breakout rooms.

STRUCTURE OF THE SESSIONS

Balancing theoretical input and practical exercises is a challenge for bootcamp organisers due to the limited duration the online format allows. On one hand, the classic lecture format is necessary to provide the audience with topic-related information. Since the participants mostly have different specialisations and levels of expertise, it is crucial to equip them with the same knowledge. These theoretical foundations build the bridge to using what they have learned via application-oriented tools and methods. On the other hand, participants frequently mentioned their need for more concrete, practical advice. The feedback proved that participants would benefit from more time dedicated to sharing hands-on experience and that they are willing to join longer sessions, even if that meant more time spent online.

The suitable time frame for online events is to be further discussed. Participants sometimes reported an imbalance between the quantity of content and the amount of time determined by the schedule. The input that is realistically possible to digest and the time dedicated to teaching and group work sometimes needs to be adjusted. That means either eliminating content from the schedule to meet the timeframe or increasing the length of the sessions and thus, of the whole event. To maintain the participants' focus during longer sessions, more breaks would be needed. Longer sessions bring a new set of challenges with the possibility of many participants dropping out due to other commitments.

HOMEWORK ASSIGNMENT

A homework assignment was part of two bootcamps, namely one at the IASSIST and the SSHOC DARIAH bootcamp. This proved to be a good way for participants to reflect upon certain topics and apply knowledge to their own professional context. As attendees often desire more hands-on exercises, homework assignments are a useful tool. They support the participants' learning process without taking time away from the bootcamp itself. Yet, only about half of the group wanted or was able to dedicate time to perform the assignments between sessions. Uploading the homework in well-structured templates and formats enabled learning from each other before the 2nd session when the homework was discussed. Usually, only around one hour was planned in those 2nd sessions to discuss the assignments. Regardless of the number of participants that handed in their assignments, this appeared to be too little for discussion and questions. Therefore, asking the participants to upload their homework before the sessions so that the organisers can prepare their feedback, is recommended.

STANDARDISED EVENT REPORTING

In the aftermath of the bootcamps, the reports from chapter two were written based on notetaking during the events, information on the participants, the presentation material and evaluation forms from participants. One can observe that the bootcamp reports are slightly different from each other with regards to collected data about participants and their evaluations. To make the events as comparable as possible and draw the most adequate conclusions, more standardised event reporting is highly advantageous.

3.3 Best Practices

DESIGN OF ONLINE EVENTS, EVENT STRUCTURE

Defining the event structure is a balancing act for face-to-face events, and for online events even more. The bootcamp organisation teams did their best to make the sessions as educational and at the same time as exciting as possible. Keeping in mind that the concentration span is shorter online than face-to-face, several tools were used to keep the participants' focus. For future events that deal with the functioning of complex tools, participants would benefit from live demonstrations during the sessions. Alternating between formats is important, too. In this regard, the learning objectives of the bootcamp define its structure. When presenting a specific tool, the event should contain as many practical exercises as possible.

Information overload seemed to be an issue for some participants, however, the type and the amount of information depend on the individual. It is recommended to request information on the participants' current role, the type of organization they are currently involved in, and their needs and expectations before the respective event. Asking about previous experience in that topic or a specific software tool might also be helpful. That information simplifies both the planning process and the event itself: the

organisation team knows how to tailor their information best to the participants' needs, and ultimately, they make sure that the people get the most out of their time and effort. For instance, it is possible to split the group at certain points of the event and give separate presentations if it is expected that the starting knowledge base is too different. Also, the organisers can hand out additional reading materials for interested persons (that are not further discussed in the sessions).

INFORMATION ON THE PARTICIPANTS

For all bootcamps, the organisers knew to what professional category the participants belong (see chapter [3.4 Stakeholder Representation](#)). These categories demonstrate important addressees for SSHOC training events. Thus, it is recommended to gather information on participants in a standardised way making sure that for each event, each participants' data (field of work, their place of residence, answers in the evaluation form) are filed. This information serves the SSHOC organisers in multiple ways in the event preparation (both content-wise and regarding the relationship between theory and practice).

HOMEWORK ASSIGNMENTS

Even though not every participant does the assignments that require extra time effort, homework is a great way to deepen the knowledge acquired in the sessions and apply it to an individual context. The assignments should be tailored to the participants' needs so that as many people as possible see a purpose in the homework and dedicate their time to it. During the event it is valuable to make time for discussing the assignment – to make learning fruitful and to support the participants in the best way possible, but also to adapt the discussion so that those who could not do the assignment would still benefit. During these bootcamps, the organisers realised that more time for questions and discussion would be needed in the future. To ensure full participation in the bootcamp sessions, the time commitment necessary to fully participate should be announced in advance.

INTERACTION

Creating space for interaction is very important in online formats since it does not happen naturally, like during breaks in analogue meeting contexts. Therefore, longer break-out sessions and creating informal meeting opportunities are required. This means, for example, opening a breakout session during breaks where participants can communicate more informally.

Generally, enough time should be planned for exchange in smaller groups. Giving more time for exchange in the breakout sessions is an appropriate measure, even if it means that the event will take longer. From the evaluations it can be concluded that the participants are willing to engage in a longer event if there are more opportunities and more time dedicated for networking and group interaction. The social side of online events is especially important in terms of persistently lowered human contact due to COVID-19.

ONLINE EVENT FORMAT

Even when on-site training is possible again, it is likely that online meetings will remain an important component in training portfolios. For a number of reasons (see chapter [3.1 Moving Online: Potentials and Challenges](#)), it will make sense to offer online-offline hybrid learning. In this regard, hybrid could be organising events that combine on-site training with a virtual online component. Its characteristic is that the participants both on-site and online should have the same event experience, and the same learning outcomes.

The open, participatory nature of hybrid events enables people independently from their (remote) location and budget restrictions to come together and share knowledge and experiences. The diversity of the participants in the online bootcamp series demonstrates that SSHOC events are relevant for people from all over the world. Providing training in a way that as many people as possible from diverse backgrounds can participate, enriches the SSHOC training offer. Furthermore, even people that live in places close to the event location could profit from online participation. Remote participation by just clicking on a link can help participants combine training with their regular work schedule, and also with work-life balance.

The heightened amount of coordination needed for online-offline hybrid events needs to be considered. For example, it may be helpful to deliver events that merely focus on specific tools for RDM only online. On the contrary, events that aim to help people develop their skills as trainers, do require face-to-face interaction. However, it is necessary to evaluate what format works well and what is appropriate for the style of the event and the desired learning outcome.

DOCUMENTATION

Storing training materials in one central spot is highly recommended. The open-access repository Zenodo¹² combines a user-friendly experience with the latest standards in research data management. For instance, all uploads get a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and support the FAIR principles (making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). Like the SSHOC project, Zenodo is funded by the European Commission.

As highlighted in chapter [3.2: Lessons Learned](#), standardised event reporting is helpful and recommended. It would be best to design a standardised evaluation form before the first event of a series. It should be assured that for every event both information about the participants and their feedback on the event are available. This is to guarantee comparability between the evaluation of different events, and also to ensure that the collected feedback is constructive (regarding structure, organization and content for

¹² Link to the Zenodo website: <https://zenodo.org/> [accessed Oct 2021].

future events). Event organisers may also benefit from making impact assessments. They could send a questionnaire to follow-up with the participants and thus, measure long-term effects of training.

In this regard, the event organisers depend on the participants' willingness to give feedback. Survey fatigue was an issue that hindered catching the experiences of all participants. This is even more of an issue for online events with a relatively short duration. As a general impression it is possibly better to collect shorter feedback during the event. More people are willing to give feedback while the event is still going whereas post-event surveys sent via email remain oftentimes unanswered.

3.4 Stakeholder Representation and Satisfaction

While the first bootcamp with 17 participants was exclusive to the SSHOC training community, the other three publicly organised bootcamps had between 50 and 100 attendees. The bootcamps attracted a variety of highly motivated participants. The stakeholder representation depended on the topic. Participants belonged to these stakeholder categories:

- Research libraries and archives;
- Universities and research-performing institutions;
- Research and e-infrastructures;
- Civil society and citizen scientists;
- Researchers.

Participants from the *research libraries and archives* group and the *universities and research-performing institutions* group were most present in the bootcamps. Among those institutions are world-class universities such as the University of Glasgow and the Institut d'études politiques de Paris (Sciences Po).

The participants' countries of residence were highly diverse: Aside from the EU-countries, for example, the bootcamps occasionally had participants from Belarus, Serbia, or India. It is remarkable that there were more participants from the United States than from the EU in the bootcamp that was part of the Global Conference of IASSIST. This indicates the relevance of other events and organizations for the promotion of SSHOC-related topics and events. Such an international audience is an impressive proof not just for its relevance, but also for the successful marketing of SSHOC and its Training Community.

TABLE 2: STAKEHOLDER REPRESENTATION – BY LOCATION

Location¹³	Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit n=17	SSHOC Train-the- Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians at the LIBER Annual Conference 2020 n=51	SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the- Trainer Bootcamp at IASSIST 2021 n=52
EU countries	11	42	17
Great Britain	4	3	8
North America (USA/CAN)	-	-	20
Russia	1	-	-
Switzerland	1	4	1
Belarus	-	1	-
Serbia	-	-	2
India	-	1	-
Philippines	-	-	1
Not specified	-	-	3

Generally, the feedback from all four bootcamps indicates a good level of satisfaction among the participants. This concerns the event organization as well as overall satisfaction with regard to whether expectations were met.

¹³ No information regarding the participants' locations was gathered for the SSHOC Train-the-Trainer RDM Bootcamp jointly organised by SSHOC and DARIAH.

TABLE 3: PARTICIPANTS' SATISFACTION WITH THE EVENT ORGANISATION

Assessment¹⁴	Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit n=17	SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians at the LIBER Annual Conference 2020 n=51
Excellently organised	50%	44%
Well organised	50%	56%
Fairly organised	-	-
Poorly organised	-	-

TABLE 4: PARTICIPANTS' OVERALL SATISFACTION WITH THE EVENT

Assessment	Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit n=17	SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians at the LIBER Annual Conference 2020 n=51	SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at IASSIST 2021 n=52	SSHOC Train-the-Trainer RDM Bootcamp jointly organised by SSHOC and DARIAH n=90
Excellent	-	56%	58%	27%
Very good	-	22%	37%	33%
Good	100%	22%	5%	33%
Fair	-	-	-	7%
Poor	-	-	-	-

¹⁴ No data regarding participants' satisfaction with the event organisation was collected for the *SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at IASSIST 2021* and the *SSHOC Train-the-Trainer RDM Bootcamp jointly organised by SSHOC and DARIAH*.

4. Conclusion

The SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps constituted an important part of building and fostering the Training Community — a major goal of SSHOC Work Package 6. By providing a platform for mutual learning and exchange, the bootcamp organisers made an important contribution to strengthening the open science community in the SSH. Although the original plan could not be complied with, the event series has been a valuable experience for multiple reasons.

It is a success that the bootcamps were offered despite the pandemic. By quickly reacting to the new circumstances, the organizers managed to adapt their schedule and to create online formats — which, naturally, could not fully replace face-to-face events, but still offered two main components of training: knowledge acquisition and mutual learning. Besides delivering RDM-specific knowledge, the bootcamp organisers shared valuable information regarding online training which was most needed at the time. They gathered knowledge on a variety of online training tools to organise events fully online at the very start of the pandemic. Therefore, members of the SSHOC T6.4 team could share their own newly gained insights into online events as part of the train-the-trainer programme.

The four bootcamps significantly and verifiably strengthened the SSHOC training community. The special value of the bootcamps consisted of the following diverse pillars: internationality, interdisciplinary, variety of topics, and the inestimably valuable human component – interpersonal exchange in the field of open science and, particularly, research data management. By combining all these elements, the organisers created an environment that offered a comprehensive learning experience. They empowered the participants in terms of familiarity with software tools and enabled collaboration across domains by assembling diverse groups of trainers. Ultimately, the participants as trainers serve as important multipliers of open science practices in a digital age.

Cloud-based infrastructures and collaboration on open research practices are key to shaping Europe's digital future. Educating and bringing together trainers from the SSH who then will share their knowledge with other stakeholders in the field of open science is highly relevant: more and more people will become advocates of a movement that promotes knowledge transfer and exchange beyond national borders. In that sense, the four SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps as part of the efforts of the SSHOC training community, took an important role in paving the way towards more open and FAIR research practices in the EU and beyond.

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List of Tables

Table 1: OVERVIEW OF THE BOOTCAMPS INCLUDING REFERENCES TO TRAINING RESOURCES AND BLOG POSTS	8
Table 2: STAKEHOLDER REPRESENTATION – BY LOCATION.....	27
Table 3: PARTICIPANTS’ SATISFACTION WITH THE EVENT ORGANISATION	28
Table 4: PARTICIPANTS’ OVERALL SATISFACTION WITH THE EVENT	28
Table 5: EVALUATION OF THE TRAIN-THE-TRAINER BOOTCAMP AT IASSIST 2021 (SUMMARISED)	33
Table 6: SSHOC DARIAH: WHERE DID YOU LEARN ABOUT THE EVENT? (SUMMARISED)	36
Table 7: SSHOC DARIAH: WHY DID YOU DECIDE TO ATTEND THE EVENT? (SUMMARISED)	37
Table 8: SSHOC DARIAH: POSITIVE IMPACT ON WORK (SUMMARISED)	37
Table 9: SSHOC DARIAH: WHAT DID YOU LIKE MOST ABOUT THE EVENT? (SUMMARISED)	37
Table 10: SSHOC DARIAH: POSSIBLE IMPROVEMENTS OF THE EVENT (SUMMARISED)	38
Table 11: SHARING FURTHER EXPERIENCES AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP (SUMMARISED)	38
Table 12: POSSIBLE IMPROVEMENTS IN TERMS OF ORGANISATION AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP (SUMMARISED)	38
Table 13: STAKEHOLDER REPRESENTATION BY PROFESSIONAL CATEGORY	39

List of Figures

Figure 1: ATTENDANCE AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP	34
Figure 2: PARTICIPANTS’ EXPECTATIONS AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP	34
Figure 3: ATTENDANCE OF BREAKOUT SESSIONS AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP	35
Figure 4: HOMEWORK ASSIGNMENTS AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP	35
Figure 5: OVERALL SATISFACTION AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP	36
Figure 6: SATISFACTION WITH ORGANISATION AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP	36

Appendix – Further Information on Bootcamp Evaluations

SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians at the LIBER Annual Conference 2020

Evaluation Survey Results (summarised)

1. Where did you learn about the event?
 - From the LIBER 2020 website.
 - From LIBERs program list.
 - Recommendation from a colleague.
 - On twitter.
2. Why did you decide to attend the event?
 - Participants see a connection to their work.
 - People are active as trainers.
 - To learn more about SSHOC.
 - For knowledge acquisition.
3. Did the event meet your expectations?
 - Met expectations (3 out of 7 answers).
 - Exceeded expectations (4 out of 7 answers).
4. Do you see this event having a positive impact on your work and how?
 - People are more aware of the SSHOC tools services.
 - One participant reported that the event allows him/her to continue to provide better support for researchers and further his/her professional career.
 - Yes, one person will share the information with colleagues.
 - Yes, the reusable materials are highly appreciated.
5. What did you like most about the event?
 - The advice on how to organise online events and make them appealing (e.g., by using games).
 - The organisers' "relaxed and knowledgeable" presentation style.
6. What did you miss or could be done better at the event?
 - There was too much information in too little time.
 - Difficulty connecting with other attendees.
7. Is there anything else you'd like to share about your experience (your suggestions/needs for expansions on the topic, etc.)?
 - "Given the challenges with COVID-19, LIBER did an exceptional job delivering this conference."

8. How well organised was the event (in terms of time management, length, venue/webinar system)?
- Excellently organised (3 out of 7 answers).
 - Well organised (4 out of 7 answers).

SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at IASSIST 2021

TABLE 5: EVALUATION OF THE TRAIN-THE-TRAINER BOOTCAMP AT IASSIST 2021 (SUMMARISED)

	<i>Generally speaking, was the workshop what you expected?</i>	<i>Do you think this workshop will enable you to apply the procedures or methods to your own work?</i>	<i>How do you rate the amount of material covered?</i>	<i>How do you rate the opportunities for questions and discussion?</i>	<i>How satisfied were you with the presentation/teaching?</i>	<i>How satisfied were you with this workshop overall?</i>
Average (On a scale from 1-5)	4.21	4.42	3.42	3.95	4.58	4.53

SSHOC Train-the-Trainer RDM Bootcamp jointly organised by SSHOC and DARIAH
Results from the evaluation survey

FIGURE 1: ATTENDANCE AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP

FIGURE 2: PARTICIPANTS' EXPECTATIONS AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP

FIGURE 3: ATTENDANCE OF BREAKOUT SESSIONS AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP

FIGURE 4: HOMEWORK ASSIGNMENTS AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP

FIGURE 5: OVERALL SATISFACTION AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP

FIGURE 6: SATISFACTION WITH ORGANISATION AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP

TABLE 6: SSHOC DARIAH: WHERE DID YOU LEARN ABOUT THE EVENT? (SUMMARISED)

Where did you learn about the event?
On twitter.
Via email.

From SSHOC mailings.
From colleagues.
On the SSHOC website.

TABLE 7: SSHOC DARIAH: WHY DID YOU DECIDE TO ATTEND THE EVENT? (SUMMARISED)

Why did you decide to attend the event?
Interest in the topic.
Interest in further educating oneself.
Active as a didactics trainer.
Work on practical cases.
The information is relevant for participants' jobs.
Better supporting researchers in RDM.
There is no internal RDM training at the participant's institute.

TABLE 8: SSHOC DARIAH: POSITIVE IMPACT ON WORK (SUMMARISED)

Do you see this event having a positive impact on your work and how?
Yes, very useful resources were presented.
Yes, the participants got new ideas on how to organise their own training activities.
Yes, more material to reflect on for the preparation of workshops.
Mixed. One participant was expecting more concrete knowledge training rather than general discussions.
One participant wouldn't call this a bootcamp. He/she got a lot of information but has "no idea" when he/she will have time to digest all that information.

TABLE 9: SSHOC DARIAH: WHAT DID YOU LIKE MOST ABOUT THE EVENT? (SUMMARISED)

What did you like most about the event?
The interactive parts, especially the breakout sessions in small groups.
The practical use cases.
The exchange with other participants because that strengthens a feeling of belonging.
The exchange with colleagues from different institutions and countries.

The balance between presentations and interaction.
Clear and efficient event moderation.

TABLE 10: SSHOC DARIAH: POSSIBLE IMPROVEMENTS OF THE EVENT (SUMMARISED)

What did you miss or could be done better at the event?
Too much reading material.
More time dedicated to group work in breakout sessions.
More time for presenting the assignments.
More time for discussion.
Considering the difference of the participants' learning status. (e.g., give some basic reading materials before the event).
Focus on in depth-learning instead of presenting more topics.

TABLE 11: SHARING FURTHER EXPERIENCES AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP (SUMMARISED)

Is there anything else you'd like to share about your experience (your suggestions/needs for expansions on the topic, etc.)?
Inviting legal experts for topics related to the GDPR.
Participants wish for more events, particularly workshops.
A two-day format is much appreciated.
Some participants wish for mor practical input and less presentation of theoretical concepts.

TABLE 12: POSSIBLE IMPROVEMENTS IN TERMS OF ORGANISATION AT THE SSHOC DARIAH BOOTCAMP (SUMMARISED)

Is there anything that would in terms of organisation make you more comfortable during the event?
Integrating more short breaks.
Participants miss in-person events.
Overall, people reported to have felt very comfortable.

TABLE 13: STAKEHOLDER REPRESENTATION BY PROFESSIONAL CATEGORY

Professional category	Mini Bootcamp n=17	LIBER n=51	IASSIST n=52	SSHOC DARIAH n=90
Research libraries and archives	9	31	6	30
Universities and research-performing institutions	5	15	38	48
Research and e-infrastructures	-	3	-	4
Civil society and citizen scientist	-	1	2	1
Researcher	1	1	-	7
Other (company)	2	-	4	-
not specified	-	-	7	-